

ISSN : 2249 - 1481

JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN EDUCATION & PSYCHOLOGY

VOL:01 No: 04

SEPTEMBER

2011

Y
F
I
H
Z
O
M

RESEARCH CELL IN EDUCATION AND PSYCHOLOGY
31/15 SUNDARAVINAYAKAR KOIL STREET
GINGEE, PIN:604 202
TAMIL NADU, INDIA
Email: jiepingee@gmail.com

CONTENTS

P.NO

- ❖ Study on instructional role perception of teachers
Working in college of education in relation to their personality traits
K.Ratheeswari & Dr.G.Visvanathan **4-10**

- ❖ A study of effectiveness of audio based lessons
In teaching of science at secondary schools
Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel & Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari **11-20**

- ❖ Achievement of higher secondary school students in chemistry related
to some influencing factors
Mrs. S.Kalaivani & Dr.R.Babu **21-23**

- ❖ A Study on Teacher Effectiveness In Relation To Job
Satisfaction of Teacher Educators
GS Prakasha, H.R Jayamma, & Thirumalesha **24-27**

- ❖ A study of anxiety and risk taking behaviour of
Secondary school students in Pondicherry region
U.Pandian & Dr.R.Ramachandran **28-33**

A STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF AUDIO BASED LESSONS IN TEACHING OF SCIENCE AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel

Associate Professor, DDE,
MANUU, Hyderabad
&

Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari

Research Assistant, CSSEIP,
MANUU, Hyderabad

Introduction:

The present era is a technology driven era. It is observed that all the aspects of society in general and human life in particular is affected and affects technology. Education is no exception in this onslaught of technology. The knowledge explosion is to such an extent that the secondary school syllabus becomes obsolete every couple of years. However, it cannot be denied that the basics provided at secondary schools are irrelevant. This is because these basics help the adolescent learner who is full of energy and enthusiasm grasps new knowledge in constructivist format. The continuous inflow of information can be brought to the knowledge of stakeholders in education through information communication technologies (ICTs) such as radio, television and internet etc. The audio, audio-visual and multimedia software are bases for such ICT programmes. Language is the base of such programmes, whether written or oral, but at the same time oral language format has also been found to be more effective irrespective of age, level and qualification of the listeners through many research studies.

The scientific discipline witnesses more frequent changes or developments in this technological era. In this scenario the teacher is forced to learn 'from technology', 'about technology' and 'with technology', so as to keep pace with the developments in educational field. Hence, there is continued change in the role of teacher and learner. There is also a felt need for development of standardized educational programmes in audio format. Dhamija (1985) found that Radio programme when mixed with certain visuals become effective. Phalachandra (2003) found that the content based Kali-Kali radio broadcast in audio format was found to be useful at primary stage. He also found that the students of radio schools have achieved better. They attend school regularly. The backward caste/ tribe children achievement is worth mentioning. These programmes have made the teachers understand the objectives, content and they have covered all the topics as described in the Keli-Kali handbook. These

programmes have enhanced the inter-school curricular competitions. In comparative study on audio graphics and face to face teach, Athar et. al. (2002) found that the learning outcomes of the audio-graphics delivery system were as successful as the conventional face-to-face one for all the courses investigated.

There are many new innovative teaching methods that are being practiced by the teachers. Few methods are still in theoretical form only. The present teacher must be aware of usage of the new teaching technology. The teacher must keep on changing the teaching method in the class room so that the students become more attentive towards the subject. The present study is based on the experiment conducted on the students to find out effectiveness of audio technique and conventional method. The findings of such a study will help the planners and policy makers to meet the demand of quality teachers, content experts, arrange for dissemination of information at larger speed without transmission loss.

Conventional teaching:

In conventional method of teaching the teacher gives lecture and asks students to memorize material for tests irrespective of knowledge of student's level of understandings. Teacher performs all the teaching activities and the students are just passive viewers and audience. The conventional or traditional mode of teaching involves teacher, students and some other intervening variable in the class. The usual teaching method adopted by a teacher in the classroom is without using much teaching aids and other modern techniques. In conventional or traditional teaching the teacher is an active facilitator who imparts the knowledge to the students and the teacher does not use much teaching aids or technology in his teaching.

In conventional teaching, teacher is the main actor and he is an independent variable, teacher organizes his teaching and imparts knowledge to the students for productive learning. The achievement of the students is more a product of teaching than

learning. The achievement of the students mainly depends on the teacher's performance.

In conventional teaching the equipments used are black board, chalk piece; pointer and teaching aids are used only when these are available. Teaching aids involve charts, models, pictures or any apparatus. The teacher superficially explains using the teaching aid and doesn't involve the students.

Audio Teaching:

Teaching is a process in which listening plays a great role, because if students listen the teacher's lecture then only they understand. Based on this principle we can impart audio lesson through Radio or CD player or any other audio aid. Audio teaching is nothing but providing instruction through audio media. The students have to hear the lessons and understand it and this requires a listening comprehension and creative imagination. This concept is not a new one, already many radio programmes are going on in which the lessons are being taught through Radio. In the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) scheme the radio lesson are compulsorily taught to the primary students. Teaching equipments which are used in audio teaching are known audio aids. Audio aids mean those sources in which only hearing organs are used i.e., knowledge gained mainly through the ears.

Nature of audio resources

It is the sounds which conveys information and stimulates the audience's imagination whether or not visual are present. The audio commentary or voice and effects bring life into the visuals in mind. Acoustic of the room where sound is recorded or audio resources played make a great deal of difference. Hard surfaces such as glass tiles and stone reflect sound, soft surfaces such as curtains, carpets and air absorb sound. Audio recording studios are arranged to have false ceilings and walls made of sound absorbing sheet of thermo coal or asbestos. The audio programmes make use of sounds. The sounds include the sound produced by human being in the form of syllable and non-sense syllables. The sounds of the animals can also be utilised for the programmes. The sound of inanimate like musical instruments, transport vehicles, cutlery, water, rain, storm, lightening also help in producing different impact on listeners of educational programmes. The pitch, speed of recording and playing also help in creation of varied impact. The judicious mix of all these and a sound planning and standardization also leads long lasting impact.

Objectives of the Study:

- To prepare the Audio programmes in Science subject of tenth standard.
- To impart the lessons through audio and conventional method of teaching.
- To compare the effectiveness of teaching among audio and conventional method.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre test-1 of Solar energy-1.
2. There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post test-1 of Solar energy-1.
3. There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre test-2 of Solar energy-2.
4. There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post test-2 of Solar energy-2.
5. There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of Control group for the unit Solar energy-1.
6. There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of Control group for the unit Solar energy-2.
7. There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of experimental group for the unit Solar energy-1.
8. There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of experimental group for the unit Solar energy-2.

Design of the study

The experimental method was used to conduct the study. The present study demands the comparison between two mode of teaching and finding the most effective methods of teaching between them. Therefore, according to Best (2010) in such situation the experimental method becomes most suitable technique to carry out the study. The pre test - post test causal comparative design was adopted for the study and pictorially it is shown in the figure 1 below:

Fig. 1 showing design of study

Sampling

The sample size was 60, 30 students formed control group and 30 students were part of experimental group. The purposive random sampling method was adopted for finalizing sample.

Control Group

In this group the teacher was asked to teach the unit using minimum teaching aids as done in case of regular classes. This mode of teaching mainly relied upon 'teaching by chalk and talk method' utilising textbooks as supplementary aids. The students activities were curtailed, their emotions, creative thinking was not given extra importance. In all this method meant very less participation of the students, less usage of teaching aids and there was no scope for students to react. The units selected for this type of teaching were same as that of the experimental group.

Experimental Group

In this type of treatment the teacher was allowed to use pre-recorded CDs developed by the investigators. The investigators collected the programmes by burning it on CDs. The intended topics in Science which were to be used in the classes along with CD and CD player were supplied to the teachers after due training. The teacher was asked to perform pre-listening and post-listening activities as described in the programme. These activities lead to active participation of the teachers and the students. The programmes had music, sound, drama and songs inbuilt into it, which helped in holding the interest of the students. Here the teacher was required to have skill of utilisation of audio aids like CD players and hence, the teacher was given prior training. Teachers were also trained regarding pre and post listening activities. They were also trained for making suitable listening arrangements.

Variables involved in the Study

Three types of variables were involved in the study.

1. *Controlled Variables* – Intelligence
2. *Independent variable*- Treatment or the method of teaching that is Conventional and Audio programme.
3. *Dependent variable* – Achievement of the students.

Tools for the study

The following tools were used in the research

1. SPM
2. Science text book
3. Audio programme
4. Lesson plan
5. Achievement test

1. SPM Test

Raven's progressive Matrices is culture fair and culture free intelligence test developed by Dr. John C. Raven in 1936. It has three versions, standard progressive matrices, advanced progressive matrices and coloured progressive matrices. Among these three the investigators used standard progressive matrices. The standard progressive matrices have 60 problems arranged into five sets of 12 items each. In each set the first problem is as nearly as possibly self-evident the problems which follow become progressively more difficult. In each problem some meaningless figures are presented. The subject has to observe it keenly see the relations between them, according to the relation the correct figure should be matched. This scale is not restricted for any particular age and any body can do it.

The test-retest reliability of the test varies from 0.83 to 0.93 for different age groups. Validity coefficient reported in studies with English and non-English speaking children and adolescents generally range up to +0.70. The content validity of SPM for different test items, correlations ranged from 0.2-0.8.

2. Science Text book

The 10th standard Physical Science text book of Karnataka state syllabus was referred. The text book is an average standard kind of text book. It has 10 topics out of which 5 are from Physics and 5 are from Chemistry. The investigators referred whole text book to get an idea for the content for selection in preparation of the experimental treatments. The text book contains enough examples, relevant experiments, required pictures and necessary important information.

3. Audio programme

The audio programme used for experimental treatment was of 20 minutes audio based lesson in which the topic Solar energy was discussed. The investigators prepared two audio programmes of 20 minutes each. The audio programme was based on discussion format. Programme had 3 characters namely, Kiran, Ahmed and teacher. The audio programmes were based on a discussion among all these three characters in a very simple language about Solar energy and Solar devices. After each audio programme, the teacher asked 4-5 questions to whom the audience students supposed was to answer. Thereby, the interactivity was in built in the audio programme. The teacher was required to do pre and post listening activities during the remaining 20 to 25 minutes of the classroom teaching.

4. Lesson Plan

The lesson plan followed the ideal format in which sub headings like, content, expected learning outcomes, teacher’s activities, pupil’s activities, black board work, and formative evaluation were clearly planned and carried out. The investigators prepared the necessary teaching aids for instruction. This lesson plan was used while teaching controlled group through conventional method there were two lesson plans prepared which took 20 to 25 minutes to teach in the classroom, and in the remaining period the students were engage in other classroom works.

5. Achievement test

The investigators prepared four achievement tests for unit Solar energy1 and Solar energy-2. The investigators prepared pretest-1 and post test1 which were both parallel testes as these were based of similar objectives. The blue print of both the tests was same, only questions were constructed on parallel by on same objectives. Similarly pre and post tests or achievement test were prepared for the unit Solar energy -2

Methods of teaching in action

Conventional method of teaching

The conventional method of teaching is nothing but the teaching in which the teacher is an active participant and more mature person who gives lecture to the pupils, who are the passive listeners. The students have to quietly listen to the teacher and try to remember the information, given so that he can recall this while writing the exams.

Preparation of Audio lesson

The present research relies on finding the effectiveness of audio programme and this is why development of the audio programme is of prime importance in the study. The investigators followed procedure of construction of this tool. The audio programme production process followed is shown pictorially as under in figure 2.

1. Conceiving the programme: The investigators roughly designed a plan showing stages involved in the preparation of audio programme. The content was also selected for the programme during this stage.

2. Writing Script: Script is the backbone and basic of audio programme. It is aptly said that if you have a good script, half of the battle is won in making a good audio programme. Before, preparing the audio script the investigators prepared the guidelines of audio script writing. The investigators divided the audio script into following parts viz.

- i. Pre listening activities
- ii. Preliminary information
- iii. Introduction
- iv. Dialogues
- v. Conclusion
- vi. Questions
- vii. Post listening activities

The above mentioned stages are a described in following paragraphs.

- i. Pre listening activities: In pre listening the investigators wrote instruction to the students for listening audio programme. These activities include classroom and out of class academic related activities. The teachers were trained before hand for conduct of these activities.
- ii. Preliminary information: This section contained the general information about the teacher and class subject etc.
- iii. Introduction: This section of script contains a brief introduction of the unit by the discussion method, which motivated the audiences to listen to whole programme.
- iv. Dialogues: This was a discussion among three characters namely, Kiran, Ahmed & Teacher on the topics Solar energy and Solar devices. The format of dialogue steps in the audio lesson plan is given with brief content from the script in figure 3.

Character	Audio	
	Dialogue	Music / sound
All the students:	Good morning Sir.	Sound of classroom and arrival of teacher
Teacher:	Very good morning to all of you.	
Ahmed:	Sir, What is this in your hand?	
Kiran:	It is a box.	
Ahmed:	Even I can see it, but what is it for?	
Teacher:	Relax, I will tell you every thing. This is one of the Solar devices named as Solar cooker.	
Ahmed:	Is it Solar cooker? (Surprisingly) But, where is the whistle?	
Teacher:	Ahmed, cooker means the one which cooks food. This need not have a whistle. Anyway, Solar cooker is a simple device used to collect Solar energy in the form of heat. This is kept in sunlight over a period of 5-7 hours during a sunny day.	

Fig. 3 showing excerpts from the audio lesson plan

Fig. 2 showing audio programme

The script was designed in such a way that the content remained focal point. The interaction was designed in such a way that the learning objectives were attained. The character of teacher explained, discussed and probed important content areas. The pauses and questions also helped to ensure audience students' involvement by building interactivity.

- v. Conclusion: The teacher asked the student characters to name different concept which they discussed and one of the student listed the content in audio programme. This it was conclusion and reinforcement for lesson.
 - vi. Questioning: Lastly the audio teacher in the lesson plan gave some home work to the students and dictated few questions.
 - vii. Post listening activities: The investigators wrote in the audio lesson plan few instructions to the teachers and students, about what activities they have to perform after listening to an audio programme.
3. Vetting and Finalizing Script: The script was corrected by investigators for which they and consulted with eminent research scholars, experts and educationist for content aspects.
 4. Conversion to final audio script: The final script was discussed with the media experts and then converted into audio script reading format (useful for participating characters and media expert). The audio script was again discussed with media expert. The investigators consulted with the media script editors and corrected the audio script. The investigators identified the characters and their voice testing was done. The script was given to most suitable voice characters.
 5. Rehearsal: The investigators called upon all the characters to gather at one place. All the characters made to read the scripts and rehearse their characteristic voice. This was continued till they become confident in playing their role. This created a comfort zone for the participants and ensured proper delivery of dialogues.
 6. Recording of programme: This was the most important step when the characters rehearsed their role. An audio studio was set in which all the characters seated comfortably. First the voice of all the characters was tested to set microphones for recording and then they read the whole script according to their role. It was a tough job for the characters because they were not the professionals; they were trained but specially for this programme. Many retake were necessary. In some situation the recording technicians in the studio asked the characters to

repeat the sentences which were not clear. It was also ensured that the final editing was made for improvement.

7. Editing: This is also a significant step where all the mistakes were corrected. The pauses or instances of confusion were removed, the repetitions of the words were cut and the other sound defects were also corrected and finally the error free audio lesson was ready.

Validity of the audio programme

Content validity: The content selected for the programme was based on the objectives set for the programme. All the intended points were covered and properly presented in the programme. This shows that the content is valid.

Concurrent validity: The programme content was based on the existing syllabus of SSLC prevailing in Karnataka. This was appropriate for present day needs. Hence, it has concurrent validity.

Construct Validity: The programme was constructed based on learning theories. Interactivity was also in built into it. Hence, it had construct validity.

Face validity: The audio programme was a representative of classroom lesson in audio format. Hence, it had face validity.

Statistical Techniques used: The investigators used statistical techniques like mean, standard deviation and t-value as referred from Mangal, S. K. (2009)

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

H1: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre test-1 of Solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 1,

Table 1, showing t-value between Control group and Experimental group for pre test-1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	4.1	1.02	0.862	2.10
Exptl	30	29	4.6	0.92		

From table 1 it is, inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 2.10 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H1 is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the means of Control group and experimental group for pretest score for the unit Solar energy-1.

H2: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post test-1 of Solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 2,

Table 2, showing t-value between Control group and Experimental group for post-test 1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	7.966	0.85	0.224	8.16
Exptl	30	29	13.8	0.886		

From the table 2 it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 8.16 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H2 is rejected. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between the means of Control group and experimental group on post test score on Solar energy1. After observing the means of both the group it can be drawn that the mean score is in favour of experimental group. That is after treatment the achievement of Experimental group is better than Control group.

H3: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre test-2 of Solar energy-2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 3,

Table 3, showing t-value between Control group and Experimental group for pre-test 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	3.93	0.82	0.242	1.23
Exptl	30	29	4.23	1.04		

From the table 3 it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 1.23 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H3 is accepted. Hence, it indicated that there is no significant difference between the means of Control group and experimental group for pre test-2 of Solar energy-2.

H4: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post test-2 of Solar energy-2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 4,

Table 4 showing t-value between Control and experimental group for post test-2 in the unit Solar energy-2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	10.93	1.04	0.279	14.33
Exptl	30	29	13.73	1.11		

From the table 4 it is indicate that the calculated value of 't' is 14.33 and the table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H4 is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between means of Control and Experimental group. Looking at the means it can be inferred that the mean score is in favour of Experimental. That means after treatment the achievement of Experimental group is better than Control group.

H5: There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of Control group for the unit Solar energy-1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 5,

Table 5, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Control group for Solar energy1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Post-test	30	29	7.96	0.85	0.24	39.93
Pre-test	30	29	4.1	1.02		

The table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 39.93 which is more than the table value. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between mean of pre-test and post-test scores of Control group in Solar energy-1. The means of both the scores indicates that Control group students perform well after teaching.

H6: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Control group for the Solar energy-2 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 6,

Table 6, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Control group for Solar energy2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Post-test	30	29	10.93	1.04	0.24	49.05
Pre-test	30	29	3.93	0.82		

The table value at 0.01 levels is 2.75 and the calculated value is 49.05 which is more than the table value. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between mean of pre-test and post-test of Control group in Solar energy-2 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Control group students perform very well after teaching unit solar energy-2.

H7: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for the Solar energy-1 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 7,

Table 7, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for Solar energy1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Post-test	30	29	13.8	0.98	0.24	12.51
Pre-test	30	29	4.63	0.92		

The table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 12.51 which is more than the table value. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between mean of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for Solar energy-1 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental group students perform very well after treatment or teaching through audio programme.

H8: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for the Solar energy-2 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' value and the results are given the following table 8,

Table 8, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for Solar energy2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Post-test	30	29	13.73	1.11	0.27	16.18
Pre-test	30	29	4.23	1.04		

The table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 16.18 which is more than the table value. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between mean of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for Solar energy-2 unit. The means of both the scores indicate that Experimental group students perform very well after treatment or teaching through audio programme.

Major Findings

1. There was no significant difference in the achievement of control group and experimental group before giving the experimental treatments for the unit Solar energy-1.
2. The students who learnt Solar energy-1 through audio method achieved significantly more than those who learnt through conventional method.
3. There was no significant difference in the achievement of control group and experimental group before giving the experimental treatments for the unit Solar energy-2.
4. The students who learnt Solar energy-2 through audio method achieved significantly more than those who learnt through conventional method.
5. When the students' pre test and post test score of control group was compared for the unit Solar energy-1, it was found that there is significant difference between two sets of achievements which means the control group students have achieved significantly more than the pre test score which also means that the conventional method of teaching Physical Science helps the students to achieve better.
6. The students when taught through the audio programme for the unit Solar energy-1, it was found that students achieved significantly more than the pre test which means the Audio programme helped the students to learn better.
7. When the students' pre test and post test score of control group was compared for the unit Solar energy-2, it was found that there is significant difference between two sets of achievements which means the control group students have achieved significantly more than the pre test

score which also means that the conventional method of teaching Science also help the students to achieve score.

8. The students when taught through the audio programme for the unit Solar energy-2, it was found that students achieved significantly more than the pre test which means the Audio programme helped the students to learn better.

Suggestion for further Research

The present study can be extended to other subjects, levels of teaching, indigenous medium of learning. The characters, formats, changing roles of teachers and taught can be studied. The live, recorded programme can be studied on small or large group. The process involved before and after the programme implementation can be studied with the process of standardization. The affective, psychomotor domain can also be studied along with cognitive development.

Conclusion

The information technology which is also based on primitive technologies like audio medium are well structured planned and effective way of teaching. These bring innovativeness and keep long lasting effect on young minds of students. Hence, teachers must try to exploit potential of such innovative and interesting media in changing technological world and in rapidly widening educational settings.

References

1. Aggarwal, J. C. (2008). Essentials of Educational Technology innovations in Teaching-Learning. Delhi. Vikas Publishing House. (Second Edition).
2. Best, John W., Kahn, James V. (2010). Research in Education. New Delhi. Prentice-Hall of India. (Tenth Edition)
3. DSERT. (2004). SCIENCE Part-1 Physics and Chemistry. Bangalore. Directorate of Text Books, DSERT.
4. Koul, Lokesh (2006). Methodology of Educational Research. New Delhi. Vikas Publishing House. (Third Edition)
5. Patel, Mushtaq Ahmed I. (2008). Audio-Visual Programmes in Teaching at schools. New Delhi. Anmol Publication.
6. Singh, Y. K. et. al. (2009). Educational Technology: Teaching Learning. New Delhi. A. P. H. Publishing Corporation.

Articles and subscriptions are sent to the following address:

Dr. K.MALINI DEVI
31/15, SUNDARAVINAYAKAR KOIL
STREET
KRISHNAPURAM, GINGEE - 604 202
TAMIL NADU, INDIA

jiepingee@gmail.com